

NEWSLETTER

January 2025

VALIAS is an Innovative Action funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101131441 (HORIZON-MSCA-2020-SE-01).

The project's main objective is to protect marine ecosystems from invasive alien species (IAS) by creating new valuable chains from their underexploited biomass feedstock.

Advanced biotechnological processes are developed and optimized to transform IAS biomass into valuable products, contributing to a circular economy while protecting marine ecosystems.

The project consortium is consisting of 8 partners from 5 countries.

The project officially began in January 2024 and its duration is 48 months.

<https://valias.eu/>

A few words from the Project Coordinator

Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR) is proud to coordinate the VALIAS Project, which brings innovative solutions to the growing challenge of invasive alien species (IAS) in European seas. Our consortium, composed of 8 partners from 5 European countries, brings together a diverse range of expertise to address the ecological and economic impacts of biological invasions.

VALIAS aims to explore nature-based solutions by utilizing selected IAS that are abundant across the Mediterranean and Atlantic coasts, turning them into valuable resources for industries such as food, feed, cosmetics and pharmaceuticals.

This innovative approach supports circular bioeconomy principles, promoting sustainable resource management while mitigating the negative effects of biological invasions.

Over the course of the project, 318 secondment months will be carried out, training at least 30 researchers in IAS management, sustainable resource use and product development. These efforts will contribute to the formulation of innovative strategies for incorporating IAS into production lines, while ensuring long-term ecosystem sustainability.

In the near future, VALIAS will organize workshops and knowledge exchange events to disseminate the project's findings to a wider audience. VALIAS will not only protect marine biodiversity but also stimulate economic growth by creating new value chains from invasive species.

Paraskevi Karachle,
Research Director at HCMR,
VALIAS coordinator

6 Work Packages

Focusing on IAS sustainable harvesting techniques and innovative biomass utilization processes. VALIAS covers everything from product development to stakeholder engagement, ensuring an efficient workflow and strong collaboration among our partners.

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101131441

Partners

1. Hellenic Centre for Marine Research (HCMR)

Coordinator of the VALIAS project, responsible for marine biodiversity research and activities related to the management of marine invasive alien species (IAS). The institution offers expertise in population management and the valorization of marine resources.

<https://www.hcmr.gr>

2. PRINSUS

Dissemination manager for the project, with expertise in communication, recovery of valuable compounds from marine IAS and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of processes and products. PRINSUS is also responsible for encapsulation and sustainability assessments.

<https://prinsus.eu>

3. Agriculture and Food Development Authority (TEAGASC)

A partner specializing in agricultural research and food development. TEAGASC is responsible for developing commercially viable products from IAS, including functional food, cosmetics and novel fish feed. They also evaluate these products for safety and commercial potential.

<https://www.teagasc.ie/>

4. University of Salento (UNILE)

Research partner specializing in species selection. UNILE works on mapping additional IAS species, collecting literature data and establishing criteria for species selection. They contribute significantly to the scientific foundation of the project.

<https://www.unisalento.it/>

5. NUEVO

Technical partner focusing on product quality assessment. NUEVO evaluates the nutritional value, quality, and performance of new aquafeed formulations from IAS. They play a key role in ensuring that the final products meet industry standards.

<https://nuevo-group.com/>

6. European University Cyprus (EUC)

Regulatory and safety partner. EUC conducts safety testing and regulatory compliance for IAS-derived products. They focus on pre-clinical safety studies and ensure that the products meet European legal standards.

<https://euc.ac.cy/en/>

7. Bantry Marine Research Station (BMRS)

Marine research specialists. BMRS works on selecting species of interest, conducting literature reviews, and performing safety tests on VALIAS ingredients. They also support environmental assessments for the project's activities.

<https://www.bmrs.ie/>

8. Physiopharma

Cosmetic development partner. Physiopharma focuses on creating anti-aging cosmetic products from IAS-derived bioactive substances. They conduct market studies, evaluate skin health benefits and assess product formulations.

<https://physiopharma.bg/>

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101131441

Dissemination material

All the necessary promotional material needed for the dissemination activities of the VALIAS project has been designed, namely:

- a banner
- a bookmark
- a brochure
- a trifold

The brochure was created in multiple languages (Greek, English, Bulgarian and Italian), corresponding to the countries involved in the VALIAS consortium.

PARTNERS

CONTACT US

Project Co-ordinator
Paraskevi K. Karachle (HELLENIC CENTRE FOR MARINE RESEARCH)

Phone
+30 2111 065217

Address
46.7 km Athens Sounio ave., P.O. Box 712, 19013 Anavyssos, Attiki, Greece

Email
pkarachle@hcmr.gr
valias.msca.project@gmail.com

FIND US

VALIAS
Valorization of Marine Invasive Alien Species (IAS) a Pathway Towards the Protection of European Marine Biodiversity: From Destructive Invaders to a Source of Wealth

Horizon-MSCA-2022-SE-01

VALIAS

Protecting marine Ecosystems from Invasive alien species (IAS) by creating new value chains from their underexploited biomass feedstock

Email
pkarachle@hcmr.gr
valias.msca.project@gmail.com

Find us

Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101131441.

Download here:
<https://valias.eu/media-kit/>

Protecting marine Ecosystems from Invasive alien species (IAS) by creating new value chains from their underexploited biomass feedstock

VALIAS AT A GLANCE

VALIAS focuses on the protection of marine ecosystems from invasive alien species (IAS) by creating new value chains from their underexploited biomass feedstock.

The project aims to create a WinWin solution via the exploitation of IAS for both European fisheries and companies active in the sector of aquaculture, nutrition and cosmetology.

- Development of new sustainable pathways of WS, leading to new products from their underexploited biomass feedstock and valorization of European marine biodiversity.
- Creation of a new sustainable source of natural safe and viable ingredients that can be integrated in an industrial business for food, feed and cosmetology ready to use.
- Cover the companies' demand for chemical-free, natural and sustainable products.
- Empower and improve the productivity of European fisheries, aquaculture, food and cosmetics sector with environmental, economic and social acceptance.

Workflow

- WP1: Management and Coordination
- WP2: Dissemination and Communication Activities
- WP3: Marine Invasive Alien species' selection, data collection for mapping
- WP4: Recovery and formulation of valuable compounds' toxicity and safety evaluation
- WP5: Development of final products of commercial interest
- WP6: Sustainability Assessment- Economic evaluation of valorization pathways

5 European countries
8 Partners
7 Work packages
48 Months
16 Deliverables
1,5M € EU contribution
5 Milestones
318 Secondment months

VALIAS

Horizon-MSCA-2022-SE-01
Valorization of Marine Invasive Alien Species (IAS) a Pathway Towards the Protection of European Marine Biodiversity: From Destructive Invaders to a Source of Wealth

318 Secondment months to implement 5 research steps

- 1 Marine invasive alien species will be selected based on collection of existing data in terms of presence (distribution), abundance, biology, ecology, toxicity and potential uses (i.e., as fishfeed, food and cosmetic industry).
- 2 Use of underexploited feedstock biomass to extract valuable compounds in high selectivity, yield and purity via green extraction methods - Evaluation of toxicity and safety of ingredients for food and feed application.
- 3 Encapsulation of bioactive compounds using proteins and/or polysaccharide mixture as carriers in order to increase bioactivity and controlled release, developing stable and safe formulations.
- 4 Development of stable and safe functional food, fishfeed and cosmetic products. Implementation of preliminary market research for VALIAS products indicating their commercialization potential.
- 5 Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) to assess the environmental impact of processes and new products - Socio-techno-economic assessment of processes for final product development.

Partners: ceagasc, PRINSUS, nuevo, Physiopharma, hcmr, BANTRY MARINE RESEARCH STATION, European University Cyprus, UNIVERSITÀ DEL SALENTO

Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101131441.

Horizon-MSCA-2022-SE-01

VALIAS
Valorization of Marine Invasive Alien Species (IAS) a Pathway Towards the Protection of European Marine Biodiversity: From Destructive Invaders to a Source of Wealth

Protecting marine Ecosystems from Invasive alien species (IAS) by creating new value chains from their underexploited biomass feedstock

VALIAS PROJECT AIMS

- Development of new sustainable pathways of WS, leading to new products from their underexploited biomass feedstock and valorization of European marine biodiversity.
- Creation of a new sustainable source of natural safe and viable ingredients that can be integrated in an industrial business for food, feed and cosmetology ready to use.
- Cover the companies' demand for chemical-free, natural and sustainable products.
- Empower and improve the productivity of European fisheries, aquaculture, food and cosmetics sector with environmental, economic and social acceptance.

CRITICAL ISSUES

- 1 Build a strategy for the control of marine IAS population through sustainable valorization pathways of this underexploited biomass feedstock.
- 2 Match the need for managing the marine IAS populations with the growing demand for marine derived ingredients.
- 2 Tackle the current problem of potential marine IAS into a 'WinWin' solution both for the European fisheries and for the companies active in the sector of aquaculture, nutrition and cosmetology.
- 4 Optimization of both green extraction methods for the selective recovery of marine derived ingredients, as well as encapsulation techniques for an increased bioactivity and controlled release of the bioactive compounds, developing stable and safe formulations.
- 5 Development of stable and safe functional food, fishfeed and cosmetic products. Exploring VALIAS products' commercialization potential.
- 6 Assessment of the environmental impact of processes and new products - Socio-techno-economic assessment of processes for final product development.

PARTNERS

8 Partners
5 European countries
318 Secondment months
48 Months
16 Deliverables
7 Work packages
5 Milestones
1,5M € EU contribution

Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101131441.

VALIAS

Horizon-MSCA-2022-SE-01
Valorization of Marine Invasive Alien Species (IAS) a Pathway Towards the Protection of European Marine Biodiversity: From Destructive Invaders to a Source of Wealth

318 Secondment months to implement 5 research steps

- 1 Marine invasive alien species will be selected based on collection of existing data in terms of presence (distribution), abundance, biology, ecology, toxicity and potential uses (i.e., as fishfeed, food and cosmetic industry).
- 2 Use of underexploited feedstock biomass to extract valuable compounds in high selectivity, yield and purity via green extraction methods - Evaluation of toxicity and safety of ingredients for food and feed application.
- 3 Encapsulation of bioactive compounds using proteins and/or polysaccharide mixture as carriers in order to increase bioactivity and controlled release, developing stable and safe formulations.
- 4 Development of stable and safe functional food, fishfeed and cosmetic products. Implementation of preliminary market research for VALIAS products indicating their commercialization potential.
- 5 Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) to assess the environmental impact of processes and new products - Socio-techno-economic assessment of processes for final product development.

PARTNERS

Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101131441.

FIND US

Secondments ✈✈✈✈✈

118 Secondments in 5 countries

By August 31st 2022, 24 secondments have been completed and 10 are ongoing (30%).

During my three-month secondment at Teagasc, Ashtown, Dublin, I had the opportunity to work under the guidance of Professor Brijesh Tiwari, focusing on the valorization of marine invasive alien species to promote European marine biodiversity protection. This experience included hands-on training in processing the seaweed species of Sargassum. I engaged in various drying and extraction techniques in order to

suggest an approach for the holistic valorization of the most significant components of Sargassum. This opportunity enhanced my skills in experimental techniques and project implementation. Overall, it was an amazing experience that broadened my horizons and significantly contributed to my professional development. Marina Stamarkou, PRINSUS

*"I'm excited to share that during my month-long secondment at the HCM, Athens, Greece, I focused on the literature review, specifically researching the sea urchin *Diadema setosum*. I delved into its abundance, biology, distribution, ecology, toxicity, and potential uses. It's fascinating to explore how this species fits into our understanding of invasive marine life!*

*My background as a phycologist has always driven me towards the blue bioeconomy. My journey started with *Sargassum* spp. in the Caribbean, and now I'm eager to explore how we can integrate various seaweeds, like *Alaria esculenta*, into sustainable bioeconomic practices." Priya Pollard, BMRS*

*"I also had a great experience during my time at HCMR, Athens, Greece. I worked on the literature review for the red seaweed *Asparagopsis armata*. As a researcher specializing in microbial biotechnology, I'm particularly interested in the bioeconomy and the potential of seaweeds as renewable feedstock for biorefineries. Understanding the ecological role of *Asparagopsis armata* is crucial for sustainable practices in marine resource management."*

Roderick Van Roosmalen, BMRS

*"Thanks to VALIAS, I had the privilege of connecting with esteemed project partners Prof. Magdalini Krokida and Dr. Sofia Papadaki during my one-month secondment at Prinsus in Athens, Greece. This experience greatly expanded my knowledge in the biological characterization of protein, fat and mineral ash content of *Lagocephalus sceleratus*, providing insights that will be invaluable in advancing my expertise in pharmacology, especially in the areas of toxicity and safety evaluation." Iva Tzvetanova, Assistant Professor, EUC*

"The Marie Skłodowska-Curie funded project has integrated researchers from multiple countries and diverse disciplines. As a PhD student in EUC, this has given me the opportunity to visit Prinsus for two months secondment and improve my laboratory skills

*and strengthen my knowledge while training in techniques new for me involving the evaluation of protein, fat and mineral ash Content in *Pterois miles*". Sophia Themistocleous, EUC*

"Thanks to VALIAS, I had the great opportunity as a PhD student at EUC to spend a one-month secondment at Prinsus in Athens, Greece. During my time there, I worked

*on the biological characterization of *Fistularia commersonii*, enhancing my expertise in instrumental analysis for protein, fat, and mineral ash content." - Chrysi Tomouzou, EUC*

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101131441

Meetings

- Kick off Meeting - January 2024
- 1st Project Meeting - March 2024
- 2nd Project Meeting - September 2024
- 3rd Project Meeting - November 2024

VALIAS Boosts Impact with Horizon Results Booster!

We're excited to announce that VALIAS has partnered with the Horizon Results Booster to receive expert guidance!

Here's how we're leveling up:

- **Module A:** *Creating a portfolio of R&I project results and mapping relevant stakeholders and target audiences.*
- **Module B:** *Designing and executing a common dissemination plan for the portfolio, including actual dissemination of results.*
- **Module C:** *Improving exploitation strategies with tailored guidance and training.*

Thanks to this support, we're ready to drive the sustainable use of IAS, amplify our results and engage stakeholders across industries to ensure long-lasting impact!

VALIAS's 1st public deliverable "Complete List of Species"

This comprehensive document identifies IAS with high invasiveness and potential for utilization in the food, fish feed and cosmetic industries. Explore the full deliverable on **Zenodo**: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14615567>

Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101131441

In Media

A poster regarding VALIAS research activities and goals was prepared by Hellenic Centre for Marine Research in the zenodo.org. Find the article here: <https://zenodo.org/records/13759454>

VALIAS: Valorization of Marine Invasive Species as a Pathway Towards the Protection of Mediterranean Marine Biodiversity: From Destructive Invaders to a Source of Wealth

Project goals:
Develop sustainable Resource Utilization (R.U.) methods to utilize IAS feeds to enhance resource management, aligning with circular economy principles.
Bring European Research through Innovation Community (ERIC) and leading sea-lice chain stakeholders to a common platform, resulting in a new and added value.
Empowering Marine Biodiversity Conservation Funding: marine bio-waste to managing IAS species feeds to reduce harm and promoting long-term sustainability in European seas.

Methods and Techniques:
Implementing Sustainable Development (SDG) and safety extraction techniques from IAS.
Optimizing feed formulations and safe feeding protocols for farmed fish production.
Developing Resource Utilization (R.U.) methods to utilize IAS feeds to enhance resource management, aligning with circular economy principles.
Bringing European Research through Innovation Community (ERIC) and leading sea-lice chain stakeholders to a common platform, resulting in a new and added value.
Empowering Marine Biodiversity Conservation Funding: marine bio-waste to managing IAS species feeds to reduce harm and promoting long-term sustainability in European seas.

Product development:
Developing Sustainable Development (SDG) and safety extraction techniques from IAS.
Optimizing feed formulations and safe feeding protocols for farmed fish production.
Developing Resource Utilization (R.U.) methods to utilize IAS feeds to enhance resource management, aligning with circular economy principles.
Bringing European Research through Innovation Community (ERIC) and leading sea-lice chain stakeholders to a common platform, resulting in a new and added value.
Empowering Marine Biodiversity Conservation Funding: marine bio-waste to managing IAS species feeds to reduce harm and promoting long-term sustainability in European seas.

Sustainability and Environmental Impact:
Assessing Environmental Impact (SDG) and safety extraction techniques from IAS.
Optimizing feed formulations and safe feeding protocols for farmed fish production.
Developing Resource Utilization (R.U.) methods to utilize IAS feeds to enhance resource management, aligning with circular economy principles.
Bringing European Research through Innovation Community (ERIC) and leading sea-lice chain stakeholders to a common platform, resulting in a new and added value.
Empowering Marine Biodiversity Conservation Funding: marine bio-waste to managing IAS species feeds to reduce harm and promoting long-term sustainability in European seas.

Outputs and Achievements:
New Resource Utilization (R.U.) methods to utilize IAS feeds to enhance resource management, aligning with circular economy principles.
Bringing European Research through Innovation Community (ERIC) and leading sea-lice chain stakeholders to a common platform, resulting in a new and added value.
Empowering Marine Biodiversity Conservation Funding: marine bio-waste to managing IAS species feeds to reduce harm and promoting long-term sustainability in European seas.

The innovative work of the VALIAS Project had been featured in **GreenAgenda!**

VALIAS is exploring sustainable solutions by utilizing IAS to create natural botox, cosmetics, food, fish feed and even leather bags. This pioneering approach opens up new opportunities for green innovation. Find the full article on the official website: <https://greenagenda.gr/>

GREENAGENDA

VALIAS: ΦΥΣΙΚΟ ΒΟΤΟΧ, ΚΑΛΥΝΤΙΚΑ, ΦΑΓΗΤΟ, ΙΧΘΥΟΤΡΟΦΕΣ, ΒΙΟΚΑΥΣΙΜΑ ΚΑΙ... ΔΕΡΜΑΤΙΝΑ ΑΠΟ ΞΕΝΙΚΑ ΕΙΔΗ (ΦΩΤΟ)

The VALIAS Project had been featured in the Greek online magazine **Agrotypos!**

The article highlights how the VALIAS Project focuses on developing alternative raw materials for fish feed production. VALIAS promotes sustainability while embracing the principles of the circular economy. Find the full article on the official website: <https://www.agrotypos.gr/>

Agrotypos

ΤΑ ΕΡΕΥΝΗΤΙΚΑ ΕΡΓΑ VALIAS ΚΑΙ FEEDACTIV

PROTIX

Ready to make waves with low-footprint, high-performing feeds?

Transforming marine invasive species into sustainable aquafeeds

The European VALIAS project is tackling the need for sustainable aquaculture practices and the ecological threat posed by marine Invasive Alien Species (IAS), seeking to convert environmental threats into economic opportunities.

We're proud to share that the VALIAS Project had also been featured on **The Fish Site!**

The article highlights our innovative efforts to transform marine invasive alien species into sustainable aquafeeds, paving the way for eco-friendly solutions in the aquaculture industry. You can find the full article on the official website: <https://thefishsite.com/>

Conferences

The VALIAS Project was represented by our coordinator, Paraskevi Karachle, at the 13th International Conference on Biological Invasions, hosted by the Faculty of Sciences at the University of Lisbon.

The VALIAS Project was presented at the Blue Economy Round Table during Monaco Ocean Week, held on the 22nd of March in Monaco, by Dr Magdalini Krokida, Professor at the School of Chemical Engineering of NTUA.

Antigoni Vasilaki presented a poster titled: "Conventional Fishmeal vs Fishmeal Produced by *Lagocephalus sceleratus* - In Vitro Evaluation" at AQUA2024 | European Aquaculture Society conference

Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101131441

VALIAS Project at European Researchers' Night 2024

**EUROPEAN
RESEARCHERS'
NIGHT**

The VALIAS project was presented in the European Researchers' Night, hosted in Athens, Greece, on September 27th. The project was presented by the PRINSUS team with great success since more than 200 persons visited their booth. The audience had the chance to be informed about how VALIAS is protecting marine ecosystems by transforming IAS into valuable resources through the development of innovative value chains. The evening also featured interactive demonstrations and engaging activities, all of which highlighted the importance of marine conservation and sustainability.

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101131441

Work progress

HydroMediT 2024

The VALIAS Project was disseminated by PRINSUS Technovlastos at HydroMediT2024 at the premises of the University of the Aegean on the greek island of Lesvos

INTERNATIONAL
**SEA TOURISM
FESTIVAL 2024**
RHODES

YACHTING | CRUISING
SAILING | WATERSPORTS
DIVING | FISHING

PRESENTED BY AYIA NAPA MARINA by OGA

The VALIAS Project was also disseminated at the International Sea Tourism Festival 2024 at Rhodes Island. Our coordinator delivered an oral presentation about invasive species and their impact on marine biodiversity.

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101131441

1st VALIAS WORKSHOP AS A SATELLITE EVENT OF Joint ESENIAS & DIAS Scientific Conference 2024 & 13th ESENIAS Workshop

The 1st Workshop of the VALIAS Project was successfully held as a satellite event on November 28th during the Joint ESENIAS & DIAS Scientific Conference 2024, in conjunction with the 13th ESENIAS Workshop, in Menemen, Izmir, Turkey. The event brought together 30 participants from 10 research institutions across 4 countries, marking a significant milestone in fostering collaboration and advancing research within the project's scope.

Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101131441

Events

The VALIAS Project was represented by PRINSUS Technovlastos at the 'Engineering a Startup' event hosted by ODYCEO at the NTUA Library

FRI 19/4 @ LIBRARY NTUA ΑΙΘΟΥΣΑ ΠΟΛΥΜΕΣΩΝ 14:30

ENGINEERING A STARTUP

How engineers can promote their ideas

BY #ODYCEO

SUPPORTED BY ORFIUM

VALIAS

Horizon-MSCA-2022-SE-01
Valorisation of Marine Invasive Alien Species (IAS) a Pathway Towards the Protection of European Marine Biodiversity: From Destructive Invaders to a Source of Wealth

218 Secondment months to implement 5 research steps

PRINSUS, NUEVO, ORFIUM, SynPharma

Funded by the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101131441

Achievements

WP3: Marine Invasive Alien Species' Selection and Data Collection for Mapping

The project team has compiled a comprehensive list of target IAS, including species such as *Asparagopsis armata*, *Sargassum*, *Crepidula fornicata*, *Lagocephalus sceleratus*, *Siganus* spp., *Fistularia commersonii* and *Diadema setosum*. Extensive data collection efforts have been conducted to map their distribution, abundance, biology, ecology and potential uses in food, feed and cosmetic industries.

WP4: Recovery and Formulation of Valuable Compounds - Toxicity and Safety Evaluation

The team has optimized green extraction methods to recover high-purity bioactive compounds from selected IAS. Encapsulation techniques using proteins and polysaccharide mixtures derived from IAS have been investigated to enhance the stability and bioavailability of these compounds.

WP5: Development of Final Products of Commercial Interest

Collaborative efforts between academic and industry partners have led to discussions about the opportunities to develop stable and safe functional food, aquafeed and cosmetic products incorporating bioactive compounds derived from IAS. Preliminary analyses will assess the commercial potential of these products, aligning with consumer demand for natural and sustainable ingredients.

WP6: Sustainability Assessment - Economic Evaluation of Valorization Pathways

Preliminary data have been selected to perform a comprehensive Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) to assess the environmental impact of the processes and products developed within the project. In this way, LCA data will be used to evaluate the overall eco-efficiency of the valorization pathways. These assessments will guide the optimization of production processes, aiming to maximize eco-efficiency by reducing environmental impact and enhancing economic output.

Find more about us on social media

 X: VALIASProject

 Facebook: Valias

 Linked In: VALIAS project

and on our website
<https://valias.eu/>

Funded by
the European Union

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101131441